

**UNVEILING THE EXPERIENCES OF PARENTS AS HOMESCHOOL
TEACHERS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC: A
PHENOMENOLOGY OF ACADEMIC
STRUGGLE AND RESILIENCE**

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Unveiling the Experiences of Parents as Homeschool Teachers During the Covid-19 Pandemic: A Phenomenology of Academic Struggle and Resilience

Analyn T. Barte, * Lyndon A. Quines

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to unveil the experiences encountered by the parents/guardians as home school teachers during the COVID-19 Pandemic within General Santos City. The study utilized a qualitative research design, specifically the phenomenological study. The participants of this study were the sixteen (16) parent participants as home school teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic within General Santos City. The data were gathered from parents as homeschool teachers through in-depth interviews. The data were gathered through in-depth interview and Focused Group Discussion (FGD) using guide questions. The use of tape recorder was availed, and varying experiences were clustered into themes for easy understanding and interpretation. The result of the study formulated three categories such as the experiences, coping mechanism, and the insights or lessons learned by the participants. The experiences of the parents as homeschool teachers during pandemic formulated 4 emergent themes and these were instructional challenges, personal challenges, technical challenges, and financial challenges. The coping strategies formulated the emergent themes resiliency, embracing family-centric values, support from family members, and collaboration. Lastly, the insights or lessons learned by the parents formulated the following emergent themes. These were learning virtual setting, learning at home, and keeping life simple.

Keywords: *educational management, homeschool teachers, parents, academic struggle and resilience, phenomenology, philippines*

Introduction

"I home school my children, not to prepare them for tests, but to prepare them for life." -Tamara L. Chilver

The statement above means that the goal of homeschooling is not solely focused on preparing children for exams or achieving good grades but rather on equipping them with practical skills and knowledge that will be useful throughout their lives. Parents may tailor their children's education through homeschooling, giving them a more specialized education that considers each child's particular needs and interests. This approach can better prepare children for the challenges they will face in the real world, including practical skills like financial literacy, cooking, and household management.

In addition, the COVID-19 epidemic has prompted an unprecedented worldwide closure of schools, which has profoundly impacted the experiences of educators, learners, and even parents during the closed months. Learning now takes place mostly at home, either on one's own or with help from family members using the various technologies that are accessible. On the other hand, most school systems typically gather their pupils in big groups for group instruction and demand daily physical attendance throughout the weekdays. Due to the pandemic, learners shifted to homeschooling instead of face-to-face classes, wherein parents served as the homeschool teachers (Bozkurt & Sharma, 2020; Bubb & Jones, 2020; Euber, 2020).

For many years, homeschooling has been a contentious issue. Homeschooling provides the ability to customize a child's education so they can learn quickly. Youngsters can advance in lessons and tackle more challenging topics if they pick things up quickly. Homeschooling makes it possible for students to have a more profound knowledge of the content being covered, which can be challenging in regular schools where pupils are sometimes put in groups based on their age or level of aptitude. It can be the best alternative if parents want to make sure their children's educational demands are satisfied while still having enough time to learn everything else, and it is a fantastic option if the child has special needs (Dong et al., 2020; Kallitsoglou & Topalli, 2021; Mifsud, 2021).

Unfortunately, identified parents in General Santos City experienced frustration due to the shifting of the school system from face-to-face classes to online classes. Parents found it difficult to adjust to the new normal. Some parents preferred the old-school system, but some preferred homeschooling or online classes to ensure the safety of their children. Because of their instincts and experiences with them, parents have a unique understanding of their children's needs, tendencies, and desires and know what is best for them. The parents are in the ideal position to help the child grow into a responsible adult because of this dynamic, which produces a unique viewpoint that no one else can imitate (Peltz et al., 2020; Thorell et al., 2022; Yeasmin et al., 2020).

Despite the extensive research on the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on education, there remains a notable research gap regarding the specific experiences of parents who have assumed the role of homeschool teachers. While studies have explored the challenges faced by students and teachers during this time, there is limited qualitative research delving into the lived experiences, struggles, and perspectives of parents as they navigate the complex terrain of homeschooling their children during the pandemic. Understanding these experiences is crucial to developing targeted support systems and interventions for parents' new educational roles.

This study on unveiling parents' experiences as homeschool teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic held significant urgency in light of the global health crisis's profound educational transformations and challenges. As the pandemic continued to disrupt traditional schooling systems, parents had been thrust into the role of primary educators with little preparation or guidance. Exploring their experiences and academic struggles would not only shed light on the immediate effects of the pandemic. Still, it would also inform educational policy, interventions, and support systems to better equip and empower parents in their crucial role as homeschool teachers. We could strive towards a more resilient and effective education system during and beyond the pandemic by addressing this urgency.

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore parents' experiences as homeschool teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. How do the participants describe their experiences as parents and homeschool teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic?
 - 1.1. what are the challenges of parents as homeschool teachers during the covid-19 pandemic;
 - 1.2. how do parents cope with the challenges they experience as homeschool teachers; and
 - 1.3. what are the insights or lessons learned by the parents as homeschool teachers?

Literature Review

Experiences of Parents as Homeschool Teachers

Limited knowledge exists regarding the impact of the COVID-19 on the daily functioning of families and children despite the severe medical consequences associated with the disease. Specifically, in efforts to mitigate the transmission of COVID-19, numerous countries implemented lockdown measures, including the closure of schools. However, schools play a vital role in providing essential services beyond education, such as nutrition, physical activity, social interaction, and mental health support. Consequently, the closure of schools may disrupt the everyday routines and functioning of children and their parents. Recent reviews and commentaries have suggested that the resulting social isolation can contribute to depression and pose mental health risks for children, including increased stress, anxiety, and family conflict, both during and after the pandemic (Bubb & Jones, 2020; Parczewska, 2021; Thorell et al., 2022).

Furthermore, empirical evidence indicates that children have commonly experienced behavioral issues such as irritability, aggression, inattention, and internalizing problems during the COVID-19 pandemic. Homeschooling has been linked to the most pronounced adverse effects of various activities. However, there is a notable absence of large-scale studies encompassing multiple countries that investigate the homeschooling experiences amid the COVID-19 outbreak. There is a hypothesis suggesting that children with existing mental health conditions might be particularly susceptible to the consequences of the pandemic. More difficulties in coping with day-to-day living, hostility, and homeschooling have been found in smaller surveys aimed at parents of children with neurodevelopmental impairments. Nevertheless, it has also been proposed that children with mental health conditions could potentially derive positive aspects from homeschooling, a claim that necessitates further exploration (Jackman et al., 2022; Maital & Barzani, 2020; Thorell et al., 2022).

Moreover, the parent/guardian group, a significant stakeholder in education, equips students with various skills to navigate life. In the past, parents primarily fulfilled cultural and socialization roles in education. Still, these roles have diminished with the expansion of educational programs offered by schools and the increasing involvement of parents in professional pursuits. Numerous studies have attempted to define the educational roles of parents, identifying them as negotiators, monitors, supporters, and advocates. As negotiators, parents discuss classroom selection, educational services, and personalized assistance required for their children. In their monitoring capacity, parents consistently evaluate the quality and content of educational programs. Furthermore, as supporters, parents provide encouragement and assistance to teachers, extending their support whenever needed (Kiral, 2020; Lee & Crunk, 2020; Šimunović & Babarović, 2020).

Lastly, in their advocacy capacity, parents can advocate for their children and teachers whenever needed. Conversely, several studies have underscored the significance of effective parent-child communication in promoting student success, shedding light on parents' pivotal role in education. These studies emphasize that parents have traditionally assumed responsibilities such as providing a safe environment and support and fostering communication as part of their educational role. However, the closure of schools and the subsequent necessity of homeschooling due to the COVID-19 pandemic have brought about a fundamental shift in the educational roles of parents/guardians. The advent of homeschooling during the pandemic has compelled parents to face unfamiliar responsibilities, thereby altering their traditional educational roles (Hefner et al., 2019; Šimunović & Babarović, 2020; Wang & Su, 2020).

Furthermore, parents' educational roles have been analyzed within the care, control, and motivation framework. The caring role encompasses responsibilities such as providing educational materials, fostering study skills and habits, and serving as a positive role model. The control role entails ensuring regular school attendance, monitoring homework completion, and questioning the quality of education their children receive. Lastly, the motivation role involves encouraging children to attend school, setting goals for their academic progress, and cultivating a positive attitude toward school. It has been observed that parents' ability to fulfill these roles may vary depending on their educational background and individual personality traits. Minimizing interpersonal contact has become paramount as a preventive measure to curb the spread of the pandemic. Consequently, deciding to close schools and transition to online

education has become crucial (Mazza et al., 2020; Parczewska, 2021; Raes et al., 2020).

Conversely, the educational approaches implemented during the COVID-19 lockdowns differed

On the contrary, the COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in unforeseen consequences, particularly impacting various groups, including children, who have become covert victims of this global health crisis. Following the closure of schools worldwide in response to the spread of COVID-19, governments and local authorities have taken measures to provide online platforms, televised and radio broadcasts, educational materials, and distance learning options to facilitate homeschooling (Bhamani et al., 2020; Garbe et al., 2020; Kallitsoglou & Topalli, 2021).

However, it has become evident that these opportunities are not equally accessible to all individuals. Despite efforts to support teachers and parents/caregivers and enhance platform accessibility, homeschooling has yielded unexpected consequences, particularly for parents/caregivers. Limited studies have explored the challenges faced by parents/caregivers during the pandemic period (Brossard et al., 2020; Hefner et al., 2019; Kiral, 2020).

After all, amidst the COVID-19 pandemic, numerous parents worldwide assumed the role of homeschooling teachers for their children. This sudden shift in responsibility presented various challenges and opportunities for parents, influenced by various factors. Homeschooling became a positive experience for some, allowing them to spend more time with their children and gain deeper insight into their learning needs. They could personalize their teaching approach based on their child's unique interests and abilities, with some reporting that their children thrived in this environment (Hatip, 2020; Matsubara et al., 2021; Parczewska, 2021).

On the other hand, homeschooling proved to be a demanding and stressful undertaking for others as they struggled to balance work and other responsibilities with the challenges of teaching their children. Some parents expressed feeling overwhelmed by the workload, while some children experienced difficulties due to the lack of social interaction and structure accompanying in-person schooling. Overall, parents' experiences serving as homeschool teachers during the pandemic were intricate and varied, revealing both the strengths and limitations of this educational approach (Beteille et al., 2020; Jackman et al., 2022; Sweetman, 2021).

Coping the Challenges of Parents as Homeschool Teachers

The rapid surge in COVID-19 cases worldwide presents a significant challenge for education stakeholders, including educators, policymakers, and curriculum developers, as it directly impacts their roles and responsibilities. The United Nations has reported that this pandemic has led to the most significant disruption of educational systems in history, affecting approximately 1.6 billion learners across more than 190 countries. In response, government institutions and the education sector are compelled to reconsider and reshape the existing curriculum to create a more sustainable framework that caters to the needs of learners in the "new normal" context (Agayon et al., 2022; Daks et al., 2020; Lee & Crunk, 2020).

Furthermore, several countries have devised educational policies to support flexible learning approaches to mitigate the adverse consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic. For example, Turkey swiftly responded to the need for a comprehensive plan to deliver quality education during the pandemic. Their measures included early school closures to prevent the further spread of the virus and the establishment of an online educational portal offering a wide array of learning materials such as videos, documents, e-books, tests, and activities for learners across all levels from preschool to high school. Additionally, they provided free internet access for remote lessons and aired a series of educational programs on three national television channels (Cahapay, 2020; Fadare et al., 2021; Griffith, 2020).

Likewise, within the Philippine educational context, the role of parents in implementing various remote learning methods during the COVID-19 crisis is crucial. The Department of Education has introduced a learning continuity plan upon reopening schools, which includes adopting remote learning in different modalities, considering the resources and circumstances of communities. An essential aspect of the plan is the emphasis on the involvement of parents in implementing these diverse learning delivery methods. For example, it highlights the need for parents to supervise technology use for early grade levels closely. However, concerns arise regarding whether parents are prepared to assume this role (Kallitsoglou & Topalli, 2021; Matsubara et al., 2021; Pimentel-Tibon, 2020).

Nevertheless, despite efforts to support parents in educating their children at home, struggles are inevitable. For instance, a survey found that during the height of the COVID-19 crisis, half of American parents reported feeling overwhelmed by the responsibility of homeschooling, leading to significant levels of depression and anxiety. Chinese parents also faced difficulties implementing online learning during the crisis, especially if they needed more training or readiness for such an approach. These experiences reflect parents' reality in this particular research and in many countries worldwide (Dong et al., 2020; Garbe et al., 2020; Lee & Crunk, 2020).

Researchers are working to record their firsthand accounts and written descriptions of their experiences during the COVID-19 epidemic. It is acknowledged that history often focuses on past experiences, but capturing history from the present moment is a challenge in extraordinary times like the current crisis. As a research approach, phenomenology offers an appropriate method for capturing lived experiences, as it explores the essence of individuals' experiences with a particular phenomenon. This approach delves into the very nature of the experience itself (Euber, 2020; Lee & Crunk, 2020; Sedibe & Fourie, 2018).

Moreover, when examining the most recent pandemics, such as H1N1 and the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, studies utilizing phenomenology as a research approach have predominantly focused on workers in allied medical fields. Some articles discuss the lived

experiences within the educational context, explicitly addressing the implications for teachers and students. While there are papers exploring how parents engage in homeschooling, they need to explore the lived experience systematically. Additionally, other works provide glimpses into parents' experiences regarding their children's education, but these studies do not specifically address a global crisis. In light of the COVID-19 pandemic, parents who are leading the way in distant learning for their kids must take into account their lived experiences, according to the synthesis of information and methodological gaps in these linked works (Cahapay, 2020; Reich et al., 2020; Wang & Su, 2020).

Additionally, homeschooling parents during the pandemic have faced the challenge of ensuring a well-rounded education that encompasses not only academic subjects but also physical activity, socialization, and emotional support. Creative approaches have been employed to address these aspects, such as incorporating regular physical activity breaks and finding online resources for socialization and emotional well-being (Hefner et al., 2019; Šimunović & Babarović, 2020; Wang & Su, 2020).

Moreover, adapting to the specific requirements of their children has posed an additional challenge for homeschooling parents. They have had to consider their child's distinct learning style and interests, and it has necessitated higher flexibility and personalized attention compared to traditional classroom-based learning. Additionally, homeschooling during the pandemic has presented financial difficulties for some families. Homeschooling requires having access to a variety of resources, including technology, supplies, and textbooks, but these costs can be incredibly taxing for families who have lost income due to the epidemic or have faced financial difficulties (Brossard et al., 2020; Hefner et al., 2019; Leeferink et al., 2019).

In conclusion, coping strategies have involved seeking cost-effective or free resources and exploring government and community programs supporting homeschooling families. While homeschooling during the pandemic has brought about numerous challenges for parents, it has also created personal and educational growth opportunities. Through the development of coping strategies, the adaptation to their children's unique needs, and the exploration of innovative approaches to provide comprehensive education, homeschooling parents have exhibited their resilience and dedication to their children's learning (Mazza et al., 2020; Parczewska, 2021; Raes et al., 2020).

Lessons Learned by Parents as Homeschool Teachers

The support provided by parents is crucial for children's education, as it improves their learning and contributes significantly to their academic achievements. Some parents with the necessary time, teaching skills, and resources may homeschool their children. The examination of how parents coordinate their children's learning and development opportunities is guided by sociocultural theories of human development. These theories help us comprehend the sociocultural environments in which young Spanish-speaking children participate, as well as how families interpret the intentions of teachers and their role as their children's first educators (Bhamani et al., 2020; Garbe et al., 2020; Susilowati & Azzasyofia, 2020).

Efforts to establish partnerships between homes and schools to reduce discrepancies between the beliefs and practices of families and schools regarding each other's expectations should consider the "cultural models" and "cultural settings" in which children are involved. As defined by Gallimore and Goldenberg, cultural models are shared ways of thinking and interpreting how the world should function. In contrast, cultural settings refer to situations where people come together to accomplish something valuable through joint activities. By examining how parents interpret and implement early childhood education practices at home during the COVID-19 pandemic, we can uncover the cultural models and settings of Latinx parents (Brossard et al., 2020; Bubb & Jones, 2020; Puccini, 2018).

Moreover, previous research has concluded that parents actively engage in their children's education, which leads to better educational and mental health outcomes for the children. Through meaningful parental involvement, parents better understand schools' cultural models and settings. This comprehensive understanding, encompassing the cultural models and settings associated with schools, is also called academic socialization. Academic socialization includes parental beliefs (cultural models) and practices (cultural settings) that create contexts in which children acquire behaviors, attitudes, and social skills beneficial for their schooling (Hefner et al., 2019; Puccini, 2018; Tasyah et al., 2021).

Additionally, the extent of academic socialization among parents varies based on their school experiences, perceptions of school expectations, and beliefs about children's learning processes. Studies examining parental academic socialization concerning literacy have found that some Mexican-American parents tend to believe that reading is acquired through a formal process involving the combination of syllables. These beliefs are influenced by the parent's own experiences of learning to read and resemble traditional methods of teaching reading in Latin America. Since many of these parents have not attended school in the United States, they are less familiar with the expectations in early childhood education programs (Mazza et al., 2020; Parczewska, 2021; Wang & Su, 2020).

Similarly, extensive research emphasizes that Latinx parents hold high educational expectations for their children and implement practices at home that promote their development. However, these practices may need to align with those used in schools. Nevertheless, cultural models are not fixed, and as immigrant parents engage in their children's education, they dynamically incorporate their perceptions of what is expected in U.S. schools. For instance, a study found that although reading aloud is uncommon in Latinx households, parents in the study started integrating it into their practices once teachers emphasized its importance (Agayon et al., 2022; Daks et al., 2020; Rasmitadila et al., 2020).

Furthermore, parental academic socialization is influenced by parents' beliefs about how children learn. Some parents adopt an entertainment-based approach, while others prioritize skill-building when teaching literacy. Parents with an entertainment perspective tend to respond to their children's interests and incorporate print materials. In contrast, those with a skills-oriented perspective believe in direct instruction and frequently use flashcards and workbooks. Notably, many low-income parents in one study held a skills-oriented perspective. In a more recent study focused on teaching mathematics, half of the parents believed that play is crucial for children's math learning, while a third emphasized practice (Cahapay, 2020; Reich et al., 2020; Wang & Su, 2020).

Furthermore, parental support remains a crucial factor in children's education, with homeschooling serving as an alternative for parents who possess the time, pedagogical skills, and resources necessary for this approach. Parents' beliefs about how children learn also influence their academic socialization practices. Some parents adopt an entertaining approach, focusing on their child's interests and experiences with print, while others prioritize skill-building through direct instruction, employing flashcards and workbooks. Notably, most low-income parents in one study held a skills-oriented perspective.

Of course, the COVID-19 pandemic has compelled parents to take on the role of homeschool teachers to ensure their children continue to receive an education amidst the disruption caused by the crisis. It has been essential for families with limited access to reliable internet or devices for remote learning. Homeschooling has allowed parents to actively engage in their child's education actively, offering greater flexibility and personalization compared to traditional classroom-based learning. Ultimately, the pandemic has underscored the essential role of parents as critical partners in education, leading to new possibilities for the delivery and experience of education.

Methodology

Research Design

The research design employed in the study was qualitative, namely the phenomenological study method.

Participants

Through purposive sampling, parents were selected as the study's respondents. These parents were selected because they were willing to share their experiences as homeschool teachers at this time. The participants of this study were 16 parents; 8 underwent an in-depth interview (IDI), and another eight went a focus group discussion (FGD). They answered the same 12 questions.

Instruments

The researcher used a research-made interview guide questions that have undergone series of validation processes. Three (3) expert validators evaluated the interview guide and their recommendations were incorporated in the paper.

Procedure

First, the logistical requirements were prepared, including the venue and audio/voice recorder used during the interview with the participants. The venue and time were determined via Zoom during the researcher's meeting.

Second, before the conduct of the interview, the participants were given a copy of the consent form to sign via Zoom and a physical meeting. It contained the study's objectives, methodology, confidentiality, and benefits, including the contact number of the researcher if there are any clarifications or verifications of the purpose. After which, with no more extended questions or clarifications, the Consent Form was retrieved. A Participant Agreement Form followed it. It indicated the agreement between the participants and the researcher for the interview and transcription process. It included the use of a pseudonym and other pertinent information to help the researcher come to know and recall each participant. Most of all, the form includes their permission to conduct the interview.

Lastly, it was followed by a one-on-one interview with the participants via Zoom and face-to-face. It consisted of two parts. The first part merely solicited information that served as the basis for the participants' backgrounds. The second part was the proper interview, which consisted of questions followed by developmental questions to gain more meaningful answers.

The participants were interviewed face-to-face, and COVID-19 protocols were observed, such as following established protocols regarding mask-wearing, physical distancing, hand sanitizing, and other preventive measures.

Since the study utilized one-on-one interviews, the researcher believed that building rapport and trust with the participants is more important than the questions in the discussion guide. The list of questions and objectives is meaningless if the participant feels self-conscious or apprehensive throughout the session. That is why the researcher initiated a preliminary meeting with the informants and explained the details of the study, making them understand that everything would be done with utmost confidentiality.

Then, I conducted one-on-one interviews with the participants at an agreed time and place at their convenience. A digital recorder was used to record the interview. Their answers in the interview were transcribed after the interview process. The participants were asked questions during the proper interview, followed by elucidating or probing questions. The main question is: When public schoolteachers retire early, look specifically at the factors or considerations influencing their decision to early retirement and their life assessment after

retirement. Asking this grand tour question allowed the freedom to tell their stories without constraint. Sub-questions in the semi-structured interview guide were also asked to elicit specific experiences.

During the interview, prompt questions were used for clarification and focus. Prompt questions include when, who, where, why, how, and what. Prompt questions were intended to lead the participant but to encourage and elicit examples and meaning about the experience they are describing. Interviews were conducted at their respective homes free of interruption, like during their free time or after their busy hours, and conducive to reflective storytelling. Each participant was interviewed separately at different times. The interviews may or may not last about an hour (van Manen & van Manen, 2021).

At the end of the interview, a leading question was asked: "Was there any experience that was not asked that you would like to share?" In most instances, this question did not elicit any new information. The researcher videotaped all the interviews, wrote a complete transcription, and used member checking to confirm the information. Participants are assured of confidentiality, as illustrated in the section of the informed consent form for human consideration. Field notes were taken during the interview to record body language or other contributing factors not reflected in the recording. It was done to minimize distractions to the participant.

Finally, the researcher transcribed the audio recordings as soon as possible after the interviews. Member checking was used as a method of validation whereby participants read and affirmed the contents of the interview transcript by affixing their signatures. Such a validation process signaled the trustworthiness of the data.

The interview saturation point is identified when the tenor of the answers has the same flow of thought deriving from the same phenomenon of experiences based on the similarity of experiences revealed during the interview.

Data Analysis

In order to reduce the gap between themselves and the participants in a qualitative study, researchers make every effort to come as near to them as they can. To analyze the data for a research project, a large amount of data must be summarized, and the findings must be presented to highlight the most critical aspects. The data analysis method included data reduction, data presentation, conclusion, drawing, and verification. It was also noted that qualitative content analysis refers to "any qualitative material and attempts to identify core consistencies and meanings" (Hunt et al., 2020).

The following steps represent the Colaizzi process for phenomenological data analysis:

The first step is reading the transcript multiple times to obtain a general sense of the whole content.

The second step is extracting significant statements that pertain to the phenomenon under study. These significant statements should be recorded on a separate sheet, noting their pages and line numbers.

The third step is formulating the meanings of significant statements. The researcher should "bracket" their presuppositions to stick closely to the phenomenon as experienced.

The fourth step is to sort the formulated meanings into categories, clusters of themes, and themes. Bracketing of presuppositions is crucial to avoid any potential influence of existing theory.

The fifth step is integrating the study's findings into an exhaustive description of the phenomenon under study, which will be presented as a narrative account. The researcher incorporated emergent themes and theme clusters and formulated meanings into the description to create the overall structure and ensure that the study contained experience elements.

The sixth step is describing the fundamental structure of the phenomenon. To match the researcher's descriptive results with the research participants' experiences, the participants themselves should be asked to validate the findings. The participants will be asked if the findings accurately reflect their experiences. Based on their responses, the researcher may decide to revise earlier stages of the study.

Results and Discussion

This portion contains the study's findings, taken from the interviews of the parent respondents who experienced becoming a homeschool teacher during a pandemic.

Categorization of Data

Three main themes came out of the responses. These are experiences, coping strategies, and lessons learned presented in the following table:

Table 1 presents the parents' experiences as a homeschool teacher during the pandemic. Several themes emerged, including instructional, personal, technical, and financial challenges. Their responses to the questions were the basis for establishing the themes.

Most of the participants shared their experiences with the difficulties of the instructions provided by the educators. This study indicated that the new instructional setup required the students' parents and themselves to adjust and adapt. It was also mentioned that they needed to prepare for the implementation of this modality. Participant 2 also mentioned that attending modules among learners requires

too much time. Participant Three discussed how the recent modality has a quick pacing with the subject matter. Likewise, participants 4 and 5 shared the same opinion about the difficulty of the lessons.

The new learning setup is complex, Ma'am. We need to adjust and adapt. We are not prepared for this.” (participant 1, lines 5-6)

This modality weighs down students with many tasks to accomplish and sometimes tricky lessons requiring too much time.

(participant 2, lines 61-63)

This modality has quick instructional pacing. Like every other week, there are new modules; my son still needs to finish the old ones. (participant 3, lines 120-122)

My daughter is worn out in learning because she sometimes complains that the lesson is too difficult. (participant 4, lines 176-177)

This modality is difficult because my child's skill level is low. (participant 5, lines 227-228)

Adjustment and learning setup, adjust time. (participant 6, line 284)

Following protocols and instructions. (FGD, line 5)

Personal challenges

Another theme that emerged from the experiences of the parents as homeschool teachers during the pandemic was personal challenges. With this, Participant 1 ensured she was uncertain about her emotions because she did not know what she would do after the shutdown. Additionally, Participant 2 believed that her child experienced blurry vision, thus making her child unable to attend online classes. Participant 3 described distance learning as an addition to their stressor because they were unprepared for the pandemic. Lastly, participant 4 shared how her son was unfocused in his lesson because her son was playing a mobile game.

I am uncertain about my emotion, Ma'am, because I do not know what to do at first. (participant 1, lines 18-19)

My child has blurry vision due to prolonged exposure to gadgets, and she sometimes complains about it.

(participant 2, lines 69-70)

Distance learning has added stress to us, both parents and learners. We are not prepared for this matter, ma'am. (participant 3, lines 133-134)

My son is unfocused during online classes, and he plays mobile games. (participant 4, lines 188-189)

It is a hard time to adjust because I am not computer literate. It is very stressful, but I have learned to adjust. (participant 5, lines 238-239)

I adjust my children's attitude because they are unfocused during online classes, but I still manage to guide them in learning the lesson. (FGD, lines 16-17)

Technical challenges

Participant 4 had independently mentioned that it was difficult for them to use the new setup because online learning needs a strong internet connection and continuous electricity supply. While they experienced technical problems. As a result, the learners would skip class or be unable to use gadgets for research.

The internet connection is our problem mostly because it is too weak in our area. Added to that is the power failure. There are unscheduled power interruptions. (participant 7, lines 341-344)

Please provide them with good signals and gadgets to use in learning. They can quickly scroll through the Internet if there is a hard lesson. (participant 3, lines 140-141)

Financial challenges

Participant 4's insight had shed light on the financial strains associated with online learning, citing increased costs for internet connectivity and electricity usage, which add to the family's financial burden. The overall impact remained significant despite potential savings from reduced daily allowances due to the lack of commuting and on-campus expenses. In contrast, traditional distance learning offers a lighter financial load, typically requiring less intensive internet usage and device dependency. These observations underscored the intricate relationship between educational delivery methods and household finances, emphasizing the need for equitable access to resources to ensure inclusive learning opportunities for all students. Because of the costly online learning, my son sometimes skips the online class, and sometimes he is delayed with the information sent by his teacher. (Participant 8, lines 397-400)

Table 1. *Experiences of the Parents as a homeschool teacher during pandemic*

<i>Clustered Theme</i>	<i>Emergent Theme</i>
Difficulty in the new learning setup	Instructional challenges

Weigh down students with many tasks to accomplish	
Allotted too much time	
Quick instructional pacing	
Worn out in learning	
Hardship with the skill level of the child	
Emotional uncertainty in learning	
Blurry vision due to long exposure to gadgets	Personal challenges
Distance Learning has added stress to both parents and learners	
Unfocused during online class	
Internet connection problems	Technical challenges
Power failure	
Costly online learning	Financial challenges

Instructional challenges

Table 2 presents the parents' coping mechanisms as a homeschool teacher during a pandemic. Several themes emerged, such as resiliency, embracing family-centric values, support from family members, and collaboration. Their responses to the questions were the basis for establishing the themes.

Resiliency

The government had received praise from the participants for its efforts to contain the pandemic and for placing the populace's health, welfare, and safety first. These participants appreciated the government's efforts to lessen the virus's spread and secure everyone's lives, especially the learners. Meanwhile, DepEd pursued continuing quality education amidst the pandemic, so different learning modalities were implemented there.

Following the government's implementation of a total lockdown on March 16, 2020, dubbed Enhanced Community Quarantine, all schools in the Philippines were shut down (ECQ). The Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BELCP), produced by the Department of Education (DepEd), offers guidelines on how the nation should deliver education during times of crisis while maintaining the health, safety, and welfare of students, instructors, and DepEd staff. In addition to policies on classroom assessment, working from home and attending webinars for teachers, moving up/graduation/recognition rites, and various alternatives for delivering distance learning during times of class suspension and similar circumstances, the DepEd also established guidelines for managing the COVID-19 situation.

Because of the pandemic, alternative learning delivery modalities were widely used in the Philippines, and I thank the government because our children are safe at home. (participant 1, lines 41-43)

The government's initiative to close educational institutions early is a big help to us parents in safeguarding our learners. (participant 2, lines 106-107)

Yes, it is helpful to contain the escalation of infectious virus." (Participant 3, line 161)

Our government prioritizes the health and well-being of the citizens. (participant 4, lines 113-114)

DepEd promoted the continuous delivery of quality education. (participant 5, lines 264-265)

I realize that during this time, we should care for our family, show love, sympathy, resilience, and respect, and coordinate with teachers and the school.(FGD, lines 44-45)

Embracing Family-Centric Values

While the lockdown gave the family enough time to spend together, the new educational design made it harder for the kids to form social bonds. The new learning environment also added to the workload for parents who were already working hard to support their families.

The student's parents knew the need to close all educational institutions and postpone the start of classes so that teachers had ample time to prepare for the new normal. Additionally, they strongly supported the government's strategic intention to assist students in continuing their education at home by adopting alternative learning delivery methods both during and after the lockdown. Numerous researchers understood the significance of the robust and positive link.

I have no more worries about children's security because of the lockdown. (participant 1, lines 27-28)

I am thankful for the government's mandate. This learning mode gives additional work for parents because we teach and guide our children. (participant 2, lines 89-92)

I am optimistic about the educational adjustments. (participant 3, lines 147-148)

Family bonding was achieved because parents as home tutors allot more time for their children. (participant 4, lines 199-200)

This setup is complex, but I could bond with my children through homeschooling. (participant 6, lines 306-307)

I adjust to the new learning setup of our children because of the pandemic. As parents, we also need to take part in teaching our children. (participant 8, lines 412-414)

With the mandate of distance learning, we got to spend quality time with our children and teach them lessons. (FGD, lines 28-29)

Support from family members

The parents of the students were aware of the need to close all educational institutions and postpone the start of classes so that teachers had ample time to be ready for the new normal. Additionally, they expressed the strong support of their families for the government's strategic plan to assist students in continuing their education at home while the country was under lockdown and beyond by using alternative learning delivery modalities.

The problem also impacted parents and students since they needed help accessing good educational resources. Many students did not have access to the Internet, and the majority could even afford to purchase the equipment necessary to take online courses. In 71 of the assessed 183 nations, less than half of the population had access to the Internet, according to a recent UNICEF report on internet access. To close the learning gap among learners, their parent's and siblings' support became crucial (Bautista & Manuel, 2020).

I loved that my children would help their younger siblings in their studies. They also give at least minimal supervision to their siblings. (participant 5, lines 258-260)

As a mother, I showed my love and care to my children and had enough tolerance to deal with them during this time. (participant 3, lines 152-153)

I constantly instill in my mind the love of my children, and because of that, I can apply varied activities for them to learn the lesson. (FGD, lines 33-34)

Collaboration

A vital link between children and schools was their parents. It was widely acknowledged and studied in education how crucial it was for parents and other caregivers to work effectively with teachers. Numerous studies had shown that parent-teacher collaboration enhanced children's academic performance, work habits, social skills, and emotional well-being. According to the OECD Teaching and Learning International Survey (TALIS) 2018, 62% of principals in the OECD believed that parents or guardians contribute "quite a bit" or "a lot" to students' academic success. Several OECD nations had incorporated guidelines on working with parents in their curriculum framework in recognition of the significance of collaboration in boosting learning outcomes for kids.

It is important. The partnership among concerned authorities is needed for the students' success and for them to become responsible learners. (participant 1, lines 47-49)

As parents, I suggest we serve as a model to our children in words, thoughts, and actions so they grow with love and concern for us. (participant 2, lines 113-115)

As parents, we should also hear their voices, sentiments, likes, and dislikes. (participant 7, 375-376)

As parents, we should be prayerful and guided occasionally in caring and teaching our children. (FGD 12, lines 49-50)

Table 2. Coping Strategies of the Parents as a Homeschool Teacher During Pandemic

<i>Clustered Theme</i>	<i>Emergent Theme</i>
Usage of alternative learning delivery modalities	Resiliency
Early shutdown of educational institutions	
Contain the escalation of infectious virus.	
Prioritize the health and well-being of citizens.	
Continuous delivery of quality education	Embracing Family-Centric Values
No more worries about children's security	
Thankful for the mandate	
Optimistic to the educational adjustments	
More time for family bonding	Support from family members
Help of younger siblings in studies	
Give Minimal Supervision	
Partnership among concerned authorities	
Responsible learners	Collaboration

Table 3 presents the lessons learned by the parents as a homeschool teacher during a pandemic. Several themes emerged, such as learning in a virtual setting, learning at home, and keeping life simple. Their responses to the questions were the basis for establishing the themes.

Learning in a Virtual Setting

Participant 1 and 2 had shared their emotions toward learning in a virtual setup. They believed that among the many advantages of online learning, students could discover that virtual education gives them access to a more flexible schedule, could lower the cost of a degree, and could make it easier for them to advance their careers while continuing their education.

The changeover proved challenging. Although educators had more time to prepare for online and hybrid classrooms, they faced many unknowns, including fluctuating infection rates and erratic decision-making. A public health emergency drove the transition online.

These success stories in virtual learning demonstrated the influence of teachers' creativity and the value of innovation in change adaptation.

I successfully used video conferencing platforms such as Google Meet and Zoom, although they were challenging to manipulate, and I was able to learn later on. (participant 1, lines 54-56)

Modular lessons are attention-grabbing. My kids need to focus on answering their modules. They use the Internet to verify their answers. (participant 3, lines 152-153)

As parents, we should have different and varied strategies for teaching our children, especially during this pandemic. Love, patience, and tolerance are my secrets.

(FGD, lines 55-57)

Learning at home

Participant 3 noted that it is okay that her daughter is staying at home and learning to ensure her safety. Participant 4 emphasized that her children were learning at home. She believed that staying home established a strong relationship with her children and that no daily allowance was needed. Meanwhile, participant 5 discussed that even though there is COVID-19, their children's learning continues. She added that the role of the teachers was irreplaceable.

Students across the country were being provided alternative resources, some online, to study outside of the classroom as a result of the widespread school closings brought on by COVID-19. The majority of students in public schools were given modules. The temporary solutions being developed for distance education range from Zoom and teacher podcasts to online classroom technologies like Google Classroom. While parents were adjusting to this new situation, students must maintain their attention on studying and refrain from excessive usage of games, social media, and movies.

Digitally literate teachers could employ online learning environments and digital materials in the classroom. Digital literacy basics will make teachers more competitive in the future, whether they practice online or in the classroom. Overall, during the COVID-19 epidemic, the instructor played a crucial role in virtual educational settings as a knowledge transmitter (Garcia et al., 2020).

It is okay that my daughter is staying at home and learning to ensure learners' safety." (participant 3, lines 162-163)

My children were learning at home. It established a strong relationship with my children; no daily allowance is needed. (participant 4, lines 213-215)

Even though COVID-19 is present, our children's learning continues. However, the role of the teachers was irreplaceable. (participant 5, lines 264-265)

Keeping Life Simple

The last theme that emerged was keeping life simple, supported by the participants' answers. Participant 1 said that this pandemic had halted busy lives like theirs. She continued by saying the pandemic had given her more time to spend with her children. Likewise, Participant 2 emphasized that she spent more time with her children. Additionally, Participant 3 supported the statements of Participants 1 and 2 that she, too, had enjoyed spending more quality time with their kids and appreciating the things surrounding them. Thus, keeping their lives simple yet enjoyable.

This pandemic has halted busy lives like ours. Moreover, it gives me more time to spend with my children. (participant 1, lines 25-28)

We spend more time together with the children. (participant 2, line 89)

This pandemic has allowed us to spend more time with our kids and appreciate what is around us. (participant 3, lines 145-147)

Family bonding was achieved because parents as home tutors allot more time for their children. (participant 4, lines 198-199)

I spent much time with my child during this pandemic. I can see the development of their learning. (participant 5, lines 251-253)

This setup is complex, but I could bond with my children through homeschooling. (participant 6, lines 305-306)

The pandemic has created a new learning setup for our children. As parents, we also need to take part in teaching our children. (participant 7, lines 374-375)

With the mandate of distance learning, we got to spend quality time with our children and teach them lessons. (FGD, lines 28-29)

Table 3. *Lesson Learned of the Parents as a home school teachers during pandemic*

<i>Clustered Theme</i>	<i>Emergent Theme</i>
Successful use of video conferencing platforms Modular lessons are an attention-grabber Ensured learners' safety	Learning in a virtual setting
Established strong relationships with children No daily allowance is needed. Irreplaceable Role of Teachers Halt busy lives Spend time together	Learning at home
Appreciate what is around.	Keeping Life Simple

Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic thrust many parents into new roles as homeschool teachers for their children. This sudden transition unearthed numerous challenges, as parents needed more preparation and support to adapt to remote learning. However, it also revealed their remarkable resilience and creativity in finding solutions to ensure their children's education continued amidst uncertainty. The stories of these parents highlighted how they overcame obstacles through hard work, flexibility, and innovation. Their unwavering commitment to their children's learning inspires them.

As we move forward, these experiences provided valuable insights that could shape the future of education. By recognizing parents' critical role in their children's schooling, we must provide them with more excellent resources and training. We should also reimagine educational systems to be more adaptable, inclusive, and resilient. The pandemic had proven that the human spirit remains unbowed, even in adversity. Let the struggles and triumphs of these parents served as a guiding light to build a brighter future for education, where love, determination, and resilience continue leading the way.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Analyn T. Barte

Jose C. Catolico Sr. Elementary School
Department of Education – Philippines

Lyndon A. Quines

Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges – Philippines